

Towards a Maturity Assessment Framework for MBSE Adoption: Domain Expert Survey

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This document is supplementary material for the paper "**Towards a Maturity Assessment Framework for MBSE Adoption: Results from a Meta-Synthesis**" and consists of the survey that was sent to domain experts for an initial evaluation of the maturity assessment framework.

1 Introduction

Thank you for participating in this early evaluation of my MBSE Maturity Assessment. This assessment is designed to help organizations navigate the transition to Model-Based Systems Engineering (MBSE) by identifying their current maturity level and highlighting key challenges, pitfalls, and best practices at each stage of adoption. Your feedback will be invaluable in refining this tool to better support organizations in their MBSE journey. Please share your insights on the structure, content, and overall applicability of the assessment. *All of the included hyperlinks in this Google Forms Page will forward you to the respective images in a Google Drive Folder.*¹

Please first read the instructions to better understand the assessment. You can find the instructions in Fig. 1.

Q1 What is your age group?

(Multiple choice - select one option)

- Under 20 years
- 20-29 years
- 30-39 years
- 40-49 years
- 50-59 years
- 60 years or older

Q2 What best describes your experience with MBSE and MBSE adoption or transition efforts?

(Multiple choice - select one option)

- I have no direct experiences with MBSE or MBSE adoption.
- I am familiar with MBSE concepts but have no practical experience.

¹ In this document, the hyperlinks are removed and the figures are included directly. For larger figures, simplified versions have been included in this document for readability. This will be indicated with a footnote. The original figures used in the survey can be found in the online supplementary material [1].

Instructions for the Maturity Assessment

The content of this maturity assessment is grounded in the findings of my (Tobias Henöckl, BSc) master's thesis, "*Navigating the MBSE Transition: A Meta-Synthesis*". Each challenge, pitfall, and best practice presented here is derived from a comprehensive synthesis of numerous scientific sources, all of which are fully documented in the thesis. For reasons of clarity and simplicity, individual references have not been included within this assessment to avoid overwhelming the reader with multiple citations. However, for those interested in exploring the specific sources behind the insights provided, all references can be found in the thesis.

Read the questions below starting with Level 1.

If you can answer all questions with "Yes", then you may continue with the questions of level 2 and so forth.

If you encounter a question of a specific level that you answer with "No", then your current MBSE adoption effort belongs to this level.

Continue with the Maturity Graph of your respective level, zoom in to a comfortable size and work your way through the challenges, pitfalls and best practices listed there. All of them are **grouped into categories** they belong to or are relevant for, displayed by the **dashed colored lines** around the boxes.

Challenges

are displayed in these boxes. They cover topics that multiple sources experienced as **challenges that have to be overcome** for a successful transition to MBSE. Usually they include a description of the challenge and sometimes a consequence resulting from handling it poorly.

Pitfalls

are displayed in these boxes. They cover **specific traps where a lot of effort, resources and time can fall into** without returning the expected progress. Similarly, they offer a description and sometimes a specific consequence that was reported.

Best Practices

are displayed in these boxes. They give **high-level instructions based on lessons learned** from multiple sources and often include consequences / rationale behind them.

The order in which the challenges, pitfalls and best practices are displayed per level **does not follow a specific ranking / rating** e.g. from more important to less important. They are solely grouped for better clarity.

Some challenges, pitfalls and best practices are **connected with a solid black line**, which should **indicate their close relation to each other**. You can either choose to follow the lines when encountered, in order to gain a deeper understanding of a specific topic which was covered by two or more elements, or first walk through each challenge then pitfall and then best practice of the specific level and afterwards look at the closely related elements for deeper understanding.

Elements that are not explicitly connected are equally important. Their inclusion reflects their specific mention or context within a particular group (challenge, pitfall, or best practice), yet these elements stand independently because they do not have a directly related counterpart in another group but remain critical to addressing the respective maturity level effectively.

Fig. 1: Instructions for maturity assessment

- I have general experience using MBSE in projects.
- I have participated in initial MBSE adoption or transition efforts.
- I have been involved in scaling MBSE across teams or organizations.
- I have extensive experience managing or consulting on MBSE adoption and transition processes.

Q3 How many years of experience do you have in this area?

(Multiple choice - select one option)

- Less than 1 year
- 1 – 3 years
- 4 – 6 years
- More than 6 years

Q4 Optional comment regarding your job or experience

(long answer text - optional)

2 Maturity Levels

Q5 Do you agree with the four maturity levels described in this assessment (see Fig. 2)?

(Multiple choice - select one option)

- (strongly disagree) 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 (strongly agree)

Q6 Optional comment on your choice for Q5: Please explain your disagreement with the maturity levels and suggest specific improvements.

(long answer text - optional)

Fig. 2: The four levels of this maturity assessment

3 Level 1: Initial Preparation

You can find Level 1 of the maturity assessment in Fig. 3².

- Q7** Do you agree with the challenges, pitfalls and best practices of this level?
(Multiple choice - select one option)
- (strongly disagree) 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 (strongly agree)
- Q8** Optional comment on your choice for Q5: If you disagree, specifically mention the challenge / pitfall / best practice and please provide reasoning (element is assigned to the wrong level / element is missing / element is unnecessary / etc.).
(long answer text - optional)
- Q9** To what extent are the following challenges, pitfalls, and best practices for “Level 1: Initial Preparation” relevant to your job or company, or have you experienced them as significant?
 For more details on each specific element, please refer to the accompanying image of this level.
(Multiple choice - select one option per challenge / pitfall / best practice in Table 1)

² For this figure, a simplified version has been used in this document for readability. The original figures used in the survey can be found in the online supplementary material [1].

Fig. 3: Level 1 of the Maturity Assessment Framework

Table 1: Relevance of challenges and best practices of Level 1

	not at all relevant 1	2	3	4	absolutely relevant 5
Understanding the value of MBSE (Challenge) (Best Practice)					
Developing common understanding about MBSE (Challenge) (Best Practice)					
Lack of skilled workforce and impact on workforce dynamics (Challenge)					
Cultural change resistance (Challenge)					
Develop holistic / systems thinking (Best Practice)					

Q10 Optional comment on your selection for Q9
(long answer text - optional)

4 Level 2: Planning & Structure

You can find Level 2 of the maturity assessment in Fig. 4².

Fig. 4: Level 2 of the Maturity Assessment Framework

Q11 Do you agree with the challenges, pitfalls and best practices of this level?
(Multiple choice - select one option)

- (strongly disagree) 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 (strongly agree)

Q12 Optional comment on your choice for Q11: If you disagree, specifically mention the challenge / pitfall / best practice and please provide reasoning (element is assigned to the wrong level / element is missing / element is unnecessary / etc.).

(long answer text - optional)

Q13 To what extent are the following challenges, pitfalls, and best practices for “Level 2: Planning & Structure” relevant to your job or company, or have you experienced them as significant?

For more details on each specific element, please refer to the accompanying image of this level.

(Multiple choice - select one option per challenge / pitfall / best practice in Table 2)

Table 2: Relevance of challenges and best practices of Level 2

	not at all relevant 1	2	3	4	absolutely relevant 5
Leadership buy-in (Challenge) (Best Practice)					
Measuring progress and ROI (Challenge) (Best Practice)					
Steep learning curve (Challenge) (Pitfall) (Best Practice)					
Tool selection and Integration (Challenge) (Best Practice)					
Define a clear scope and goals (Challenge)					
Fast false start (Pitfall)					
Think big, start small, evolve (Best Practice)					
IT infrastructure (Pitfall) (Best Practice)					
Focus on the purpose of the MBSE adoption (Best Practice)					
Establish a MBSE core team (Best Practice)					
General planning and management proposals (Best Practice)					
Knowledge transfer and collaborative learning (Best Practice)					
Change process management (Best Practice)					
Tool access (Best Practice)					

Q14 Optional comment on your selection for Q13
(long answer text - optional)

5 Level 3: Pilot Projects

You can find Level 3 of the maturity assessment in Fig. 5².

Fig. 5: Level 3 of the Maturity Assessment Framework

Q15 Do you agree with the challenges, pitfalls and best practices of this level?
(Multiple choice - select one option)

- (strongly disagree) 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 (strongly agree)

Q16 Optional comment on your choice for Q15: If you disagree, specifically mention the challenge / pitfall / best practice and please provide reasoning (element is assigned to the wrong level / element is missing / element is unnecessary / etc.).

(long answer text - optional)

Q17 To what extent are the following challenges, pitfalls, and best practices for “Level 3: Pilot Projects” relevant to your job or company, or have you experienced them as significant?

For more details on each specific element, please refer to the accompanying image of this level.

(Multiple choice - select one option per challenge / pitfall / best practice in Table 3)

Table 3: Relevance of challenges and best practices of Level 3

	not at all relevant 1	2	3	4	absolutely relevant 5
Clear Modeling Purpose (Challenge) (Pitfall) (Best Practice)					
Off-cycle vs. on-cycle decision (Challenge) (Best Practice)					
Standardization in Modeling Language Usage (Challenge) (Pitfall) (Best Practice)					
Plan and build a good model architecture (Pitfall) (Best Practice)					
Shaky foundation / Sunk cost fallacy (Pitfall) (Best Practice)					
Lack of tool support (Pitfall)					
Start MBSE with new projects (Best Practice)					
Validation and verification of models (Best Practice)					
Facilitate communication (Best Prac- tice)					
Customize and integrate tools (Best Practice)					

Q18 Optional comment on your selection for Q17
(long answer text - optional)

6 Level 4: Scaling MBSE Adoption

You can find Level 4 of the maturity assessment in Fig. 6².

Fig. 6: Level 4 of the Maturity Assessment Framework

Q19 Do you agree with the challenges, pitfalls and best practices of this level?
(Multiple choice - select one option)

- (strongly disagree) 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 (strongly agree)

Q20 Optional comment on your choice for Q19: If you disagree, specifically mention the challenge / pitfall / best practice and please provide reasoning (element is assigned to the wrong level / element is missing / element is unnecessary / etc.).
(long answer text - optional)

Q21 To what extent are the following challenges, pitfalls, and best practices for “Level 4: Scaling MBSE Adoption” relevant to your job or company, or have you experienced them as significant?
 For more details on each specific element, please refer to the accompanying image of this level.
(Multiple choice - select one option per challenge / pitfall / best practice in Table 4)

Q22 Optional comment on your selection for Q21
(long answer text - optional)

Table 4: Relevance of challenges and best practices of Level 4

	not at all relevant 1	2	3	4	absolutely relevant 5
Model complexity and flexibility (Challenge) (Best Practice)					
Reusability and model libraries (Challenge) (Pitfall) (Best Practice)					
Increased model management (Challenge) (Best Practice)					
Models as the main artifact (Challenge) (Pitfall) (Best Practice)					
Leverage the network effect (Best Practice)					
Focus on the underlying data, not just the diagrams (Best Practice)					

7 Maturity Assessment Questions

You can find the questions for the determination of the respective maturity level in the online appendix [1].

- Q23** Do you agree that the questions in the maturity assessment accurately reflect the most relevant aspects for MBSE adoption across all four levels?
(Multiple choice - select one option)
- (strongly disagree) 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 (strongly agree)
- Q24** Optional comment on your choice for Q23: If you disagree, please explain your disagreement with the questions and suggest specific improvements.
(long answer text - optional)

8 Overall Maturity Assessment Rating

- Q25** Do you think this maturity assessment is meaningful for evaluating and supporting MBSE adoption?
(Multiple choice - select one option)
- (not at all meaningful) 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 (extremely meaningful)
- Q26** Would you consider using this maturity assessment for your job or company?
(Multiple choice - select one option)
- (definitely not) 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 (absolutely yes)
- Q27** Optional comment on your choice for Q25 and Q26: Please provide the reasoning behind your answer. Why do you think that way?
(long answer text - optional)

References

1. Henoeckl, T., Verbruggen, C., Bork, D.: Towards a maturity assessment framework for mbse adoption: Results from a meta-synthesis - supplementary material (Apr 2025). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15224260>